

Determination of polyphenols (gallic acid) : For estimation of polyphenols a standard curve is first drawn as described below. Gallic acid solution is prepared. 20 ml of magnesium chloride solution (1%) was taken in each of ten 50 ml measuring flasks and 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5 and 5.0 ml of gallic acid solution (0.1%) were added to the successive flasks. The pH of the mixture in each flask was maintained at 8 using buffer solution. Finally, the volume was made upto 50 ml. This was done to keep the concentration of gallic acid in the flasks between 10 to 100 ppm. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min and absorbance of the solutions was measured at 610 nm. Unknown concentration of gallic acid can be estimated from the Beer's plot so obtained.

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Pyrolysis of Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Ti(IV) Chelates of 4,5-Dimethyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone Oxime

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IN continuation of our studies on 4,5-dimethyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone and its oxime^{1,2}, the present work reports the thermal behaviour of Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Ti(IV) chelates of 4,5-dimethyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone oxime (DMHAO). A possible correlation of the thermal stability with the structure of the chelates is reported.

Experimental

Metal chelates of DMHAO were synthesized as reported earlier³. The elemental analyses of the complexes is reported in Table 1 which show the composition of the complexes as 1 : 2 (metal :

ligand) except Ti(IV) which is 1 : 1. Thermogravimetry of the chelates was carried out in the Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar. The initial weights (mg) of the samples were 224.4, 153.0, 177.6, 173.0 and 215.0 of Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Ti(IV) chelates, respectively.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND COLOUR OF THE METAL COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	Metal
PdL ₂	Yellow	51.66 (51.86)	5.16 (5.18)	6.00 (6.05)	23.03 (23.06)
CuL ₂	Buff	57.40 (57.20)	5.73 (5.72)	6.71 (6.67)	15.10 (15.14)
NiL ₂	Green	57.80 (57.87)	5.73 (5.78)	6.72 (6.75)	14.20 (14.15)
CoL ₂	Pink	57.90 (57.83)	5.77 (5.78)	6.72 (6.75)	14.16 (14.20)
TiO(OH)L	Yellow	46.30 (46.34)	5.01 (5.02)	5.35 (5.40)	18.33 (18.50)

Results and Discussion

According to Nikolaev *et al*⁴ water eliminating below 150° can be considered as the crystal water and water eliminating above 150° may be due to water coordinated to the metal ions. In the present studies it is observed that all the chelates decompose after 200° which suggests the unhydrated nature of the chelates. The initial decomposition temperatures from the thermogram curves are taken as measure of thermal stability of the chelates. The decomposition temperatures of the chelates are reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PYROLYSIS DATA OF METAL CHELATES OF DMHAO

Chelate	Dec. Temp. °C	Initial weight mg	Residue, mg		Error mg
			Exp. value	Theoretical value Metal Oxide	
Pd	280	224.4	48.5	51.48 59.26	1.98
Cu	240	153.0	30.0	23.16 29.00	1.00
Ni	280	177.6	32.0	25.13 31.98	0.02
Co	200	173.0	31.0	24.56 31.23	0.23
TiO	200	215.0	60.0	39.77 66.35	6.35

The thermogram of the Pd(II)-DMHAO chelate shows that the weight of the chelate remains constant upto 260° and above that a continuous loss of weight is observed upto 540° indicating the decomposition of the chelate. The weight of the product remains constant (79.0 mg) from 540-620°. This weight is much higher than the theoretical value of palladium oxide. This may be due to the presence of carbon with palladium oxide because further loss in weight of the product was observed at 640 to 720°. The weight becomes constant (48.5 mg) from 720° to 800°. This value is very close to the weight of palladium indicating that metallic palladium remains in the product.

The data in Table 2 show that the thermal stability of the chelates under study is in the order Pd(II), Ni(II) > Cu(II) > Co(II) > Ti(IV), while the solution stability⁴ for the chelates is Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II). Both Cu(II) and Ni(II) form square planar complexes⁴ with DMHAO; Ni(II) chelate is less stable in solution but decomposes at a higher temperature than the Cu(II) chelate. This indicates that the thermal stability of Cu(II) and Ni(II) chelates do not depend upon the strength of the coordinative metal-ligand bond, and the decomposition of the chelates do not begin by the scission of the metal-ligand bond⁵. The thermal and solution stabilities of the Co(II) chelate is less than Cu(II) and Ni(II) chelates. This may be due to tetrahedral geometry of the chelate⁴.

The thermogram curves of the Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Ti(IV) chelates show the continuous loss of weight of the chelates and the weight becomes constant from 680°, 680°, 720° and 680°, respectively which correspond to their oxides.

The data in Table 3 reveal that the chelates of DMHAO are thermally more stable than those of salicylaldoxime^{5,6}, nioxime^{5,6}, 2-hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone oxime⁷, but have almost the

TABLE 3—DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURES OF Pd(II), Cu(II) AND Ni(II) CHELATES IN °C

Ligand	Pd(II)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)
DMHAO	280	240	280
2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime	285	225	275
2-Hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone oxime	220	220	270
Salicylaldoxime	197	170	240
Nioxime	170	130	240

same thermal stability as the chelates of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime (HNO)⁸. The higher thermal stability may be due to the introduction of two CH₃ groups (electron releasing) at positions 4 and 5 in the benzene ring which tends to increase the thermal stability of the chelates. In other words it can be said that the increase of electron density at the reactive centre increases the thermal stability of the chelates. In the case of HNO chelates, an additional aromatic ring is present which increases the electron density at the reactive centre^{9,10}. Therefore, the thermal stability of the chelates of DMHAO and HNO are almost the same.

It is, therefore, concluded that DMHAO is a better thermogravimetric reagent than salicylaldoxime, nioxime and 2-hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone oxime.

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Formation Constants of Metal Chelates of N-m-Tolyl-p-Methoxy Benzohydroxamic Acid (TMBHA) with Some Transition Metal Ions

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N-m-TOLYL-p-METHOXY benzohydroxamic acid (TMBHA) has been used recently in our laboratory in the extraction of some metal ions^{1,2} and also in the preparation of metal chelates for studying probable geometry³. The present note describes for the first time pH-metric determination of the formation constant of Fe(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) chelates with N-m-tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid in 50% ethanol-water mixture.

All the chemicals used were of AR grade and the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The ligand was prepared by the literature method¹. Metal nitrates (AR) were dissolved in double distilled water and the metal contents estimated volumetrically by titrating against standard EDTA solution using suitable indicators.

The experimental method employed consists of pH titration of the following solutions, thermostated at 27°, against 0.01 M NaOH: (A) 0.1 M KNO₃ + 0.01 M HNO₃; (B) 0.1 M KNO₃ + 0.01 M HNO₃ + 2.5 × 10⁻³ M ligand (TMBHA) and (C) 0.1 M KNO₃ + 0.01 M HNO₃ + 2.5 × 10⁻³ M ligand (TMBHA) + 5 × 10⁻⁴ M metal solution. Ionic strength was maintained μ = 0.11 M and the volume of mixture was adjusted to 50 ml by adding other solvent. The ethanol-water mixture was kept 50% v/v.

The proton-ligand stability constant of the ligand was determined from the plot of pH-meter reading against \bar{n}_A , considering the value of pH meter reading corresponding to $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. In this case, pK = 10.9, which is in good agreement with the

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